

Phenomenological Philosophy of Action: Action and the Action-Field

This paper is the third in a series:

Paper 2 — The Subjectivity and Objectivity of Morality

Paper 3 — An Alternative Path in the Philosophy of Law: A Constructivist Approach

Paper 4 — Conferred Power: Where Power Comes From and Where It Goes

Abstract:

This essay undertakes a Kantian transcendental deduction of Greimas's narratological "Modèle actantiel," elevating it into a general principle of action. Action is first divided into the phenomenological *agentive*—the experience of voluntary autonomy—and the ontological *acted*—its unknowable noumenal ground. The actantial model is then reconstructed across three axes: the axis of desire (Subject/Object), the axis of communication (Sender/Receiver), and, most extensively, the unfinished axis of power (Helper/Opponent). The essay identifies a critical omission in Greimas's power-axis: the *bystander*, an undifferentiated neutral matrix from which helpers and opponents emerge. The bystander's capacity for *le regard* (the gaze) is shown to produce profound power effects—objectification, transparentization of the action-field, and an inhibiting effect that suppresses differentiation itself. The second part unfolds a typology of the action-field into four irreducible dimensions: the physical field (spatio-temporal form), the logical field (cognitive form), the social field (intersubjective form, grounded in mutual perception and the gaze), and the cultural field (the historical synthesis of the first three dimensions, where cognitive schemas are sedimented and transformed). The argument draws on Husserl, Schopenhauer, Sartre, Foucault, Fichte, and Berkeley to establish a phenomenology of action in which the field and its neutral bystanders are constitutive transcendental conditions.

Keywords: phenomenology of action; actantial model; agentive and acted; action-field; bystander; the gaze (*le regard*); transcendental deduction; axis of power; intersubjectivity; objectification; panopticism; *différance*; Greimas; Schopenhauer; Sartre

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I. A Transcendental Deduction of the “Modèle actantiel” (Actantial Model)

Greimas’s “Modèle actantiel” reduces the characters and their variants in any narrative text to six roles, grouped into three pairs of relations: “Sujet/Objet” (Subject/Object), “Destinateur/Destinataire” (Sender/Receiver), and “Adjuvant/Opposant” (Helper/Opponent). These three pairs constitute three axes: the “axe du désir” (axis of desire), i.e., the relation of the Subject seeking the Object; the “axe de la communication” (axis of communication), i.e., the Sender emitting a value and the Receiver receiving it; and the “axe du pouvoir” (axis of power), i.e., the helping or hindering of the Subject’s attainment of the goal.

Here I intend, by means of a Kantian transcendental deduction, to elevate this model into a general principle of action and to subject it to certain modifications.

1.1 The Agentive and the Acted

Before beginning the transcendental deduction, we need to distinguish between two aspects of action itself. Analogous to Saussure’s “signifiant” (signifier) and “signifié” (signified), I divide action into two levels: the agentive in the phenomenological sense and the acted in the ontological sense.

The agentive is the experience of the autonomy of the will that the agent undergoes in acting; it is the mode in which the noumenal acted appears within the phenomenal realm. This autonomy need not be ontological; it need only be phenomenological. It constitutes the inner experiential structure of our actual decision-making. In acting, the agent experiences himself as capable of initiating an action. This is the immediate givenness of action as phenomenon. Yet this phenomenological experience is not sourceless; it points to an unknowable ground that triggers it.

The acted is precisely this unknowable, noumenal ground that triggers the phenomenological experience of the agentive. “Der Wille, als das Wesen seines eigenen Leibes, offenbart sich zunächst in den bewussten Bewegungen dieses Leibes, insofern diese nichts anderes sind als die Sichtbarkeit der einzelnen Willensakte. Diese Sichtbarkeit ist mit dem Willensakte unmittelbar und völlig gleichzeitig, ist mit ihm Eins; nur dadurch, dass sie in die Form der Erkenntniss übergeht, d.h. Vorstellung wird, unterscheidet sie sich von ihm. (The will, as the essence of one’s own body, reveals itself first in the conscious movements of this body, insofar as these are nothing other than the visibility of the individual acts of will. This visibility is immediately and completely simultaneous with the act of will, is one with it; only by passing over into the form of knowledge, i.e., becoming representation, does it distinguish itself from it.)” Schopenhauer, by taking the body as the objectification of the will, already hinted at this dimension: bodily movement is both action in the phenomenal world and the manifestation of the noumenal will. Yet the noumenal will itself is unknowable. I do not intend to adopt Schopenhauer’s ontological commitments, but I do adopt his formal insight: the acted manifests itself within the cognitive order as the phenomenological experience of the agentive, while the structure of the acted itself, its causal mechanisms, all lie beyond the boundary of the cognitive order. The transcendental deduction of the actantial model thus acquires an ontological foundation.

It must be noted, however, that even though Schopenhauer anchors the thing-in-itself as will, he still recognizes that the noumenal will itself is unknowable. We know it only through its immediate manifestation in bodily action, not its intrinsic properties, because these lie beyond the boundary of cognition. That the agentive is the manifestation of the acted must likewise acknowledge the hiatus between the order of being and the order of cognition. The acted itself is unknowable; we know only that in the phenomenological experience of action it manifests as the experience of the agentive. The actantial model is a transcendental analysis of this structure of manifestation, not an assertion about the properties of the acted itself. Every experience of action is a phenomenological immediate givenness, not a noumenal structure. Therefore, the transcendental deduction of the actantial model that follows is exclusively an analysis of the agentive, not an assertion about the acted.

1.1.1 Action and the Action-Field

Any action transcendently and logically presupposes both the action itself and the field in which the action occurs. Action always takes place within a certain field; no action can occur in an ontological vacuum.

Action is action precisely because it is the operation of something within a situation. If the situation is eliminated, action ceases to be action; it either degenerates into pure inner consciousness—yet even consciousness possesses an “intentionaler Horizont” (intentional horizon)—or into an abstract point without extension. The very concept of action already contains the distinction between the agent and a dimension beyond the agent. The agent is the initiating subject-pole of the action, and the field is the initiating situation-pole of the action. These two are not empirically contingent companions but logically necessary co-constituents. An action that bears no relation to any field is unthinkable: it would have no means of unfolding, nor could it be identified

as action.

This distinction becomes especially clear on the phenomenological level. As stated above, the agentive is the experience of voluntary autonomy that the agent undergoes in acting. This experience cannot occur in a vacuum; in experiencing himself as capable of initiating an action, the agent necessarily also experiences that this action unfolds within a certain situation. Even the most inward decision of the will already presupposes an intentional field. The field need not be physical space; it is more akin to a logical place, the dimension in which action can unfold. If this dimension is abolished, the agent's agentive loses the very possibility of phenomenological experience as action.

Thus, the action-field is the transcendental condition for the possibility of action. It is not something that the agent encounters only after the action has begun, but rather a logical place implied in the concept of action itself. The agent and the action-field are two sides of action: one is the subject-pole that initiates the action, the other is the situation-pole in which the action unfolds. Both are jointly presupposed by the concept of action.

1.1.2 Axis I: "Sujet/Objet" (Subject/Object)

Every action, when cognized, has a subject. This is not an empirical observation of action but a transcendental condition for the intelligibility of action. A subjectless action is unthinkable; it could only constitute a physical event without origin. Once we deny the subject of action, we become incapable of constituting any cognition of the world, and the world in cognition would thereby sink into an absurd, unintelligible something.

This proposition found its foundation in the phenomenological tradition. Husserl, in his *Ideen zu einer reinen Phänomenologie und phänomenologischen Philosophie* (*Ideas Pertaining to a Pure Phenomenology and to a Phenomenological Philosophy*), disclosed the fundamental structure of consciousness: "Jedes Bewußtsein ist Bewußtsein von etwas (Every consciousness is consciousness of something)." Consciousness is always intentional; it is always directed towards some object. But intentionality is not merely the form of consciousness directing itself towards an object; it simultaneously presupposes that consciousness belongs to a subject. A consciousness without a subject would be an impersonal consciousness, and an impersonal consciousness is unthinkable. Even if we provisionally suspend the subject as a substantial entity, the intentional act itself already presupposes a subject-pole that emits the intention. Husserl called this subject-pole the "das transzendente Ego" (transcendental ego). "Das transzendente Ego ist nicht ein Stück der Welt, sondern das substratlose Subjekt aller Geltungen und Gegenstände. (The transcendental ego is not a piece of the world, but the substratum-less subject of all validities and objects.)" "Das transzendente Ego ist das, was im radikalen Sinne das Subjekt aller intentionalen Bewußtseinsenerlebnisse ist, das identische Zentrum, auf das sich alle Bewußtseinsakte beziehen. (The transcendental ego is, in the radical sense, the subject of all intentional conscious experiences, the identical center to which all conscious acts refer.)"

Within the narratological dimension, this subject-pole manifests as the first person of narrative. Any action, once narrativized, must necessarily be attributed to a subject.

Even when a narrative adopts the grammatical third person, the meaning of the narrative still depends on the reader attributing the action to an identifiable subject. A narrative entirely without a subject is unintelligible, for it would be a series of unowned events, and a mere series of events does not yet constitute a narrative. The first person of narrative is not a grammatical person but the logical person of action attribution. Greimas's actantial model places the "Sujet" (Subject) at the core of the axis of desire precisely because any meaning-structure must presuppose a subject that seeks an object and initiates an action. Without a subject, there is no desire, no action; we are compelled to presuppose this logical place in order to guarantee the possibility of cognition.

It must be noted, however, that this acting subject—including the subjects in the intersubjective field discussed later—is not necessarily human. As Nagel proposed with "what it is like for a bat to be a bat," we cannot in fact assert that only humans possess subjectivity. Both anthropocentrism and panpsychism are philosophically groundless assertions; I intend to suspend this contradiction. But in order to clarify the question of subjectivity, I will propose that, for any given individual, only beings that are recognized as subjects possess subjectivity. This does not mean that beings who are not recognized lack subjectivity, but that, for an other who does not recognize them, they indeed cannot be treated as subjects.

Every action has an object. An objectless action is unthinkable; it would be a misplaced, directionless pointing-to-nowhere. "Jedes Bewußtsein ist Bewußtsein von etwas (Every consciousness is consciousness of something)," and every action is likewise an action directed towards something. We cannot operate with a directionless arrow within the cognitive order, and thus we cannot cognize a directionless action within it.

This proposition is likewise a core insight of phenomenological analysis. Husserl's "Intentionalität" (intentionality) reveals not only that consciousness always belongs to a subject but also that consciousness is always directed towards an object. This object need not be a physical entity, but it must be the correlate of consciousness. Consciousness without an object is not consciousness but an empty contentlessness. Similarly, action without an object is not action but a directionless operation. It would merely be a physical event, not an agentive manifestation of the acted brought forth by a subject. Action is action precisely because it is directed towards something.

The minimal object is what Schopenhauer called "das unmittelbare Objekt" (the immediate object), namely, the body itself. "Das unmittelbare Objekt ist der eigene Leib, vermöge dessen uns die übrigen Objekte erst gegeben sind. (The immediate object is one's own body, by virtue of which the remaining objects are first given to us.)" In *Die Welt als Wille und Vorstellung* (The World as Will and Representation), Schopenhauer points out that the body is the direct objectification of the will. "Der Leib ist für mich das unmittelbare Objekt; er ist der Ausgangspunkt meiner Anschauung der Welt. (The body is for me the immediate object; it is the starting point of my intuition of the world.)" "Jede wahrhafte Willenshandlung ist sofort auch eine Handlung des Leibes; die Bewegung des Leibes ist nichts anderes als die gesehene, in Raum und Zeit eingetretene Willenshandlung. ... Die Willenshandlung und die Leibeshandlung sind nicht zweierlei objektiv verschiedene Zustände, die durch das Band der Kausalität verbunden sind,

sondern sie sind Eins und dasselbe, nur auf zweierlei Weise gegeben: einmal ganz unmittelbar, das andere Mal in der Anschauung für den Verstand. (Every true act of will is also at once an act of the body; the movement of the body is nothing other than the seen act of will, entered into space and time. ... The act of will and the act of the body are not two objectively different states linked by the bond of causality; they are one and the same, given only in two different ways: once wholly immediately, the other time in intuition for the understanding.)” Bodily movement is both the manifestation of the will and the will’s first object. Even if the agent is not conscious of any external object, his action still has his own body as its object. Stripped of Schopenhauer’s ontological commitments, we can conclude that the body, as a physical entity, in any case occupies the logical position of the object within the monad of action. This is an irremovable position of the object in the actantial model: even if no external object is targeted by the action, the agent’s own body already fills this logical position as “das unmittelbare Objekt” (the immediate object).

In complex action, the object can be a physical entity, an abstract state of affairs, or a symbolic expression. But this empirical diversity does not alter the logical position of the object. The “Objet” (Object) in the actantial model is not an empirical goal of action, but the transcendental condition that endows action with directionality. Cancel the object, and action loses its direction; it ceases to be action.

In the narratological dimension, the object is that which the subject seeks in the narrative. Greimas calls the relation between subject and object the “axe du désir” (axis of desire): the subject desires the object, seeks the object, and the meaning of the action is conferred by this seeking. Any narrative must presuppose an object that the subject wishes to attain; otherwise the narrative loses its dynamic. Even the simplest narrative already presupposes an object. A narrative without an object is unintelligible, for it answers no question of what for. The question “what for?” is itself an inquiry after the object.

Therefore, the object is a transcendental condition for the possibility of action. Together with the subject, it constitutes the first axis of the actantial model: the subject as the initiating pole of action, the object as the direction-pole of action; the two are inseparable. There is no subjectless object, nor an objectless subject; they each establish themselves in this separation. Action is the movement of the subject towards the object. The axis of subject and object is the logical structure that any action must presuppose in order to be cognizable as action. Both are jointly presupposed by the concept of action and are the two pillars of the actantial model.

1.1.3 Simple Action and Complex Action

Having clarified the axis of subject and object, we can now distinguish between types of action. Here, I distinguish between simple action and complex action.

Simple action, which can also be called meta-action or atomic action, is the subject’s action upon “das unmittelbare Objekt” (the immediate object). As stated above, “das unmittelbare Objekt” is the body itself in Schopenhauer’s sense. Simple action is the most direct operation of the will upon the body; it depends on no external object and presupposes no complex intentional chain. As an indivisible actantial unit, it is the minimal unit of the action-chain—this is precisely why I call it meta- or atomic.

In meta-action, the subject and the object are directly identical: the body is both the emitter of the will and the will's first object. "Die Willenshandlung und die Leibeshandlung sind nicht zweierlei objektiv verschiedene Zustände, die das Band der Kausalität verknüpft, sie stehn nicht im Verhältniss von Ursache und Wirkung; sondern sie sind Eins und dasselbe, nur auf zwei gänzlich verschiedene Weisen gegeben: einmal ganz unmittelbar und einmal in der Anschauung für den Verstand. (The act of will and the act of the body are not two objectively different states linked by the bond of causality; they do not stand in the relation of cause and effect; rather, they are one and the same, given only in two completely different ways: once wholly immediately, and once in intuition for the understanding.)" Here, the bodily activity that appears as the immediate manifestation of the will is precisely meta-action. Meta-action is the atom of action; it cannot be further divided. Its hallmark is the primal experience of the agentive, that is, an indivisible active intervention of the will into a physical event. Any unit smaller than this—such as a nerve impulse or a muscle contraction—is no longer action but a mere physical event. For if the experience of the agentive is abolished, action is no longer given as action; it then no longer manifests as the phenomenal presence of the acted but is merely a causal chain on the noumenal level. Meta-action is therefore the phenomenological atom of action, the minimal unit in which the acted manifests as the agentive.

Complex action is an action-chain formed by multiple simple actions. It is composed of countless meta-actions strung together; each link is a complete meta-action, each possessing a subject and an immediate object. Yet these meta-actions are not piled together at random; they are threaded through by a unified intentionality, which may be called a will-chain. This will-chain is not external to the meta-actions; it is the exercise, by the subject within each meta-action, of a "hypothetischer Imperativ" (hypothetical imperative) of the will, which continuously projects itself in time as a series of interconnected agentive experiences. Here, each meta-action serves as a means pointing towards the next meta-action, ultimately aiming at the terminal object of the entire action-chain. This terminal object is no longer an immediate object but a mediate object, an intentional object. It need not be a physical entity; it can also be an abstract concept.

The possibility of complex action rests precisely on the atomicity of simple action. Because every simple action is a self-sufficient, indivisible unit of action, they can be strung together by a will-chain into an action-chain. If atomic action did not exist, then any complex action would lose its stable constituent links, and the will-chain would have nothing to string together. The indivisibility of meta-action is thus the transcendental condition that enables complex action to maintain its intentional unity. Every meta-action is a complete agentive experience; the will-chain is the unification of these agentive experiences in time.

1.1.4 Axis II: "Destinateur/Destinataire" (Sender/Receiver)

After establishing the axis of Subject and Object, the second axis of the actantial model emerges. The subject is the initiating pole of action, the object the direction-pole. But action is not only something done by someone, directed towards something; it is also something enacted by one agent and received by another. This dimension is

anchored in Greimas's actantial model as the "Destinateur" (Sender) and the "Destinataire" (Receiver), constituting the core of the axis of communication. The axis of subject and object handles seeking; the axis of sender and receiver handles enactment and reception. The two are mutually irreducible, and together they form the complete skeleton of the meaning-structure of action.

Whenever an action is cognized, it is attributed not only to a subject but also to a sender. The subject accounts for the performance of the action; the sender accounts for the generation of its meaning. In meta-action, the subject and the sender coincide: at this moment, the subject is both the executor of the action and the sender who enacts its meaning. In this process, the subject invests the meta-action with its meaning. Without a sender, action would be merely a physical event, not an agentive operation endowed with a meaningful direction. In other words, subject and object describe the chain of action and the chain of will; sender and receiver describe the chain of *différance*, because the enactment and reception of meaning are themselves operations of difference and deferral.

The distinction between sender and subject is this: the subject is the initiator of the action, while the sender is the bestower of the action's meaning. In simple action, the two coincide; in complex action, they can diverge. In a legal act, for example, the legislator enacts the law, but the interpretation of the law is often carried out not by the legislator. Here, the sender does not necessarily execute the action directly, yet endows the entire chain of legal acts with normative meaning. The sender is the source of meaning in the actantial model, the first "interpretant" in the semiosis of action.

The phenomenological ground of this distinction lies in the fact that action is not only the direct operation of the will upon the body, but also the active endowment of meaning by the will. Schopenhauer regarded bodily movement as the visibility of the will, a view that already implies the dimension of the sender: the will not only drives the body but also invests bodily movement with meaning. Action is not a blind impulse but an operation that signifies something. The sender is the logical place of this signification.

In the narratological dimension, the sender is the source of values in the narrative. Greimas placed the sender at the core of the "axe de la communication" (axis of communication) precisely because the values of any narrative are not self-generated but are bestowed by some sender. In mythical narrative, the sender is an oracle, fate, the king; in modern narrative, the sender may be society, conscience, the individual himself. However the empirical filling of the sender may vary, the logical position of the sender is irremovable. Cancel the sender, and the narrative loses its source of value; action loses the direction of its meaning.

At the same time, whenever an action is enacted, it necessarily presupposes a receiver. The sender enacts meaning, and this meaning must be received by some receiver; otherwise the meaning hangs in the void, unactualized. In meta-action, the receiver can be the agent himself. The individual enacts the meaning of the action and also receives it: here, the individual's experience of the action is precisely the reception of meaning.

The minimal receiver is the agent himself. Even if no external other receives the

meaning of the action, the agent himself already occupies the logical position of the receiver. The individual gives himself the law, receives it, and executes it. This is the minimal closed circuit of the meaning-structure of action. Cancel the receiver, and the sender's enactment loses its direction; meaning cannot be realized. In other words, a meaning that no one receives is not a meaning but a monologue.

In complex action, the receiver can separate from the sender, and indeed often does. The legislator enacts the law, and the receivers of the law are the citizens; the teacher transmits knowledge, and the receivers are the students; the orator delivers a speech, and the receivers are the audience. The empirical filling of the receiver can be plural: individuals, groups, society, and so on.

The logical necessity of the receiver consists in the fact that the meaning of action must be completed in reception. The sender enacts meaning, but meaning is not unilaterally determined by the sender; it is always generated in difference. Meaning is differed and deferred in the process of transmission; the receiver's very act of reception is an operation of *différance* upon the meaning, stripping it from the sender's context and placing it into the receiver's context, thereby generating new differences. The receiver thus becomes another node of the "interpretant." The meaning of action is not the monologue of the sender, but a dialogue between sender and receiver. Cancel the receiver, and meaning loses the field in which it is completed; action degenerates into a hollow enactment without response.

The sender and the receiver together constitute the axis of communication in the meaning-structure of action. The sender is the source of meaning; the receiver is the destination of meaning. The two are inseparable: there is no sender without a receiver, for sending is always sending to someone; nor is there a receiver without a sender, for receiving is always receiving of something. The meaning of action is enacted, differed, deferred, and received along this axis. But it must be noted that the receiver is not a terminus but the starting point of a new *différance*. The meaning of action is enacted, differed, deferred, received, and re-enacted along this axis. The axis of communication is thus the manifestation of the infinite movement of *différance* within the meaning-structure of action.

1.2 The Unfinished Axis: Axis III: "Adjuvant/Opposant" (Helper/Opponent)

After establishing the "Sujet/Objet" (Subject/Object) "axe du désir" (axis of desire) and the "Destinateur/Destinataire" (Sender/Receiver) "axe de la communication" (axis of communication), the third axis of the "Modèle actantiel" (actantial model) comes into view. The subject is the initiator of action, the object its direction; the sender is the enactor of the action's meaning, the receiver the recipient of that meaning. But action never takes place in a vacuum inhabited only by the agent and the transmitters of meaning. As stated in 1.1.1, action always unfolds within a field, and the field is not merely an empty physical space but always contains the presence of others. Here, the influence of these other forces within the field upon the action constitutes the third axis of the actantial model: the axis of power.

Greimas anchored this axis as "Adjuvant" (Helper) and "Opposant" (Opponent). The "Adjuvant" is the force that aids the achievement of the action, the "Opposant" the

force that hinders it. In narrative texts, the “Adjuvant” is the ally, the helper, the opportunity; the “Opposant” is the enemy, the obstacle, the predicament. Greimas’s classification stems from the empirical analysis of a large number of narrative texts, but for the sake of the transcendental requirements of a general theory of action, we must subject it to a transcendental deduction.

1.2.1 The Transcendental Condition for Field-Forces to Enter the Action-Situation

That the action-field necessarily contains forces other than the agent has already been demonstrated in 1.1.1. If the field is the dimension in which action unfolds, then it cannot be an absolute nothingness. A field of absolute nothingness is equivalent to no field at all, for if the field is nothingness, it possesses no dimension whatsoever for action to unfold. Hence, the action-field logically must contain dimensions beyond the agent. These dimensions can be physical—such as the natural environment, tools, the physical presence of others—or symbolic—such as rules, discourses, networks of meaning—or institutional—such as laws, organizations, social structures.

However, one should not assume that every force existing in the field actually enters the situation of action and exerts a helping or hindering influence. For a force to influence the action, it must satisfy the transcendental condition of being perceived, that is, it must possess the possibility of being perceived by the agent.

The transcendental condition of being perceived was once formulated by Berkeley as “*Esse est percipi*” (the being of sensible things is to be perceived). In his *A Treatise Concerning the Principles of Human Knowledge*, he pointed out: “A little attention will discover to us that the very being of an idea implies passiveness and inertness in it, and that it is impossible for any idea to do anything of, or be, any way changed by, an unperceiving substance, or to exist in any other substance than a spirit or mind. Whence it seems to follow, that the objects of sense are nothing else but so many sensible qualities or combinations of sensible qualities, and what is called the ‘thing’ itself is nothing but those qualities considered together. But, answer you, the thing itself exists without the mind. I ask, what is that thing itself? If you say it is the substance which supports those qualities, I desire to know what is meant by that substance. And if, after all, you cannot tell me what it is, you must acknowledge that you do not know what you mean by it. To me it is evident that the being of a spirit or thinking thing is to think, and the being of an unthinking thing is to be perceived.”

But Berkeley made “to be is to be perceived” an ontological assertion, which runs counter to the hiatus between the order of cognition and the order of being. After discarding his ontological ambitions, we can derive a purer fact of the cognitive order: To be is to be perceivable, and to be perceived is to be able to affect. If a force within the action-field is to help or hinder the action, it must be capable of entering the agent’s perceptual horizon. A force that is not perceived is not within the situation of the action. This does not mean that an unperceived force does not exist on the ontological level; rather, it means that, for this action, it does not constitute part of the situation. It may have causally influenced the action on the noumenal level, but as long as it has not manifested in the agent’s phenomenological experience, it is not a force within the action-situation. The agent cannot respond to it, cannot incorporate it into the deliberation of the will, and cannot identify it as help or hindrance.

Here, I reformulate this proposition as: To be is to be perceivable. Its meaning within the theory of action is this: it is the transcendental threshold through which a field-force passes from its existence as a “Ding an sich” (thing-in-itself) to its existence for the action. Only by crossing this threshold does a force enter the situation of the action and become a possible helper or opponent.

1.2.2 “Adjuvant/Opposant” (Helper/Opponent): The Two Logical Modalities of Influence

Once a force has entered the action-situation, its influence on the action has only two logical modalities: helping or hindering. This is an application of the law of excluded middle within the theory of action. It must be noted, however, that these two modalities are exclusively descriptions of influence; the “Adjuvant/Opposant” are differentiated here according to the principle of influence, and they do not exhaust all that other beings in the action-field are in terms of existence or perception.

Action has a direction; it runs from subject to object. This is a structural feature of the “axe du désir” (axis of desire). The influence of a field-force upon the action essentially depends on the comparison between the direction of that force and the direction of the action. If the direction of the force coincides with the direction of the action, it helps the achievement of the action; if the direction of the force does not coincide with the direction of the action, it hinders the achievement of the action.

These two modalities are logically complete. Any force that enters the action-situation either is aligned with the direction of the action or is not. There is no third logical possibility. Even if a force empirically produces both help and hindrance at the same time, it can still be analyzed, on the logical level, as a composite of the two modalities: certain aspects of it are helpers, other aspects opponents. The completeness of the logical modalities is not shaken by empirical composites.

Therefore, “Adjuvant/Opposant” are not two classes of empirical characters but the logical places of the two logical modalities by which field-forces influence action. They are necessary presuppositions for action to unfold within a situation. A claim that a given action has no helpers refers, in reality, merely to the non-fulfillment or non-recognition of the position of the helper; similarly for the claim that an action has no opponent. To abolish these two logical positions would be equivalent to abolishing the very proposition that the field has any influence on action, which would reduce the action-field to an absolute nothingness and thereby partially abolish action itself.

1.2.3 The Forgotten Bystander

At this point, it may seem that we have completed the transcendental deduction of the axis of power. Yet Greimas’s model, and the narratological analyses to date, have all omitted a crucially important logical position: the neutral, or the bystander. Here I will use the term “bystander” to designate it.

Helpers and opponents are not primordially given. The first thing that action encounters in its situation is not forces already differentiated into help or hindrance, but others that have not yet manifested any directionality. These others are simply present, merely having the possibility of intervening, but they have not yet adopted any directional intervention. From the perspective of the action, the directional force of

these others is undetermined—neither aligned nor opposed. They exist in an undifferentiated state.

I call this logical position the bystander. The bystander is the common matrix of helpers and opponents. When the agent perceives forces within the field, these forces initially present themselves as bystanders. Only when the agent further identifies the relation between the force's direction and his own action's direction does the bystander differentiate into helper or opponent.

Greimas's axis of power presents only the result of differentiation—the opposition between helper and opponent—and omits the matrix from which they differentiate. This omission is not accidental. In narrative texts, the bystander is often ignored because his influence on the action is minimal. In almost all texts up to now, we have scarcely found authors devoting extensive description to this position, because it usually does not serve the author's intention. Narrative always focuses on those forces that drive or obstruct the action, and thus those forces that merely are present, merely gaze, do not become the focus of the narrative. Only in modern times, represented by figures like Lu Xun, has the bystander begun to enter the scene as an element of social observation and literary writing. However, viewed from the transcendental structure of action, the logical position of the bystander is irremovable. Without the bystander as a matrix, the differentiation of helpers and opponents would be sourceless; without the continuous presence of the bystander, the action-field would lose its most primordial openness.

The existence of the bystander reveals a deep structural feature of the axis of power: the differentiation of helpers and opponents is not fixed, but dynamic and reversible. A bystander can differentiate into a helper or an opponent; a helper or an opponent can also revert to the state of a bystander. The forces within the field flow among these three modalities, which ensures that the situation of action always retains a certain indeterminacy—this is the real condition that the agent must confront in his volitional decision.

1.2.4 The Mechanism of Differentiation: The Operation of the Axis of Power

The occurrence of differentiation from the bystander matrix depends on two factors: the actual direction of the force, and the agent's perception of that direction.

The actual direction of the force is the substrate on the level of the order of being; it is unknowable. The agent can identify the direction of the force only through perception. When the agent perceives that a certain force is aligned with the direction of his own action, that force is differentiated as a helper; when he perceives a misalignment, it is differentiated as an opponent. Forces whose direction remains unperceived, or whose direction has not yet manifested, remain as bystanders.

This mechanism of differentiation reveals an intrinsic connection between the axis of power and the axis of communication. The agent's perception of the field-forces is itself already an act of interpretation. The agent incorporates the force into his own cognitive schema, endowing it with the meaning of help or hindrance. In this sense, the differentiation of helper and opponent is an extension of the "Destinateur/Destinataire" (Sender/Receiver) axis into the "axe du pouvoir" (axis of power): here, the agent occupies the position of the receiver, receiving the directional signals sent by the field-forces and interpreting them as help or hindrance.

But interpretation is not arbitrary. The actual direction of the force constitutes a constraint upon the interpretation. The agent may misjudge, mistaking a helper for an opponent or an opponent for a helper, but such misjudgment will encounter resistance from the actual direction of the force in the course of the action. This is one of the phenomenological sources of the failure or obstruction of action: the agent discovers that the one he took for an ally is in fact an obstacle, or that the one he took for an obstacle can in fact become an ally.

With this, the transcendental deduction of the “axe du pouvoir” (axis of power) is complete. The helper and the opponent are the logical places of the two logical modalities by which field-forces influence action; the bystander is their common matrix, the primordial state of field-forces prior to differentiation. Together, these three constitute the dimension of power that action necessarily faces in its situation. Cancel any one of these positions, and the structure of the action-field is incomplete.

1.2.5 The “le regard” (Gaze) of the Bystander and Its Power Effects

The logical position of the bystander was established in 1.2.3 as the matrix of helpers and opponents. But the presence of the bystander does not merely signify an undifferentiated state of potentiality; apart from being a matrix, it possesses another crucial status: the bystander, as the bearer of “le regard” (the gaze), potentially exerts an influence upon the subject, the helpers, and the opponents alike. The “le regard” is not a trivial accompanying phenomenon; it has significant power effects that fundamentally alter the character of the action-field and react back upon the mechanism of differentiation of helpers and opponents.

1.2.5.1 The Gaze as a Force of Objectification

When the agent perceives the presence of bystanders in the field, he perceives not only the existence of the bystanders but also another fact, namely, that the bystanders are gazing at him. This perception has structural consequences: it activates the agent’s position as an object.

In 1.1.2, we established the logical position of the agent as subject. But in acting, the agent does not occupy only the subject position. When he becomes aware that he is being gazed at, he simultaneously occupies the position of an object—he becomes the object of the other’s gaze. The agent is transformed from a mere initiator of action into a composite of subject and object: he is at once the subject in action and the object being gazed at.

“... jusqu’à ce moment, je n’avais pas de ‘moi’ : j’étais un pur regard sur le monde, une conscience non-réflexive, absorbée par son objet. Mais voici que l’autre me regarde, et aussitôt je suis ‘vu’, je deviens un objet pour l’autre, je perds ma liberté et ma transcendance. (... up to that moment, I had no ‘myself’: I was a pure gaze upon the world, a non-reflective consciousness absorbed by its object. But now the other looks at me, and immediately I am ‘seen’; I become an object for the other, I lose my freedom and my transcendence.)” Sartre, in *L’Être et le Néant* (Being and Nothingness), analyzed the phenomenological structure of “le regard” (the gaze). When the other gazes at me, I become aware that I have become an object in the other’s world. I am no longer a pure subject; my transcendence is transcended by the other’s transcendence; I

am fixed as an object within the other's gaze. In *L'Être et le Néant*, Sartre concretely illustrated this mechanism through the keyhole example: "Supposons que j'en sois venu, par jalousie, par intérêt, par vice, à coller mon oreille contre une porte, à regarder par le trou d'une serrure. Je suis seul et sur le plan de la conscience non-thétique (de) moi. Cela signifie d'abord qu'il n'y a pas de moi pour habiter ma conscience. Rien, donc, à quoi je puisse rapporter mes actes pour les qualifier. Ils ne sont nullement connus, mais je les suis, et, par là seulement, ils portent en eux-mêmes leur totale justification. Je suis pure conscience des choses et les choses, prises dans le circuit de l'ipséité, m'offrent leurs potentialités comme réplique de ma conscience non-thétique (de) mes propres possibilités. Cela signifie que, derrière cette porte, un spectacle se propose comme 'à voir', une conversation comme 'à entendre'. [...] Mais voici que j'entends des pas dans le corridor : on me regarde. Qu'est-ce que cela veut dire ? C'est que je suis soudain atteint dans mon être et que des modifications essentielles apparaissent dans mes structures — modifications que je puis saisir et fixer conceptuellement par le cogito réflexif. D'abord, voici que j'existe en tant que moi pour ma conscience irréfléchie. [...] Cette irruption du moi, on la décrit le plus souvent ainsi : je vois moi parce qu'on me voit. (Let us imagine that, moved by jealousy, curiosity, or vice, I have pressed my ear against a door and looked through a keyhole. I am alone and on the plane of non-thetic consciousness (of) myself. This means first of all that there is no self to inhabit my consciousness. Nothing, therefore, to which I can refer my acts in order to qualify them. They are in no way known, but I am them, and by this fact alone they carry their total justification in themselves. I am a pure consciousness of things, and things, caught in the circuit of my selfness, offer me their potentialities as a reply to my non-thetic consciousness (of) my own possibilities. This means that behind that door a spectacle offers itself as 'to be seen,' a conversation as 'to be heard.' ... But then I hear footsteps in the corridor: someone is looking at me. What does this mean? It means that I am suddenly affected in my being and that essential modifications appear in my structures—modifications that I can grasp and conceptually fix by means of the reflective cogito. First of all, I now exist as myself for my unreflective consciousness. ... This irruption of the self is most often described as follows: I see myself because I am seen.)" The gaze makes me aware that I am seen by the other, thereby wrenching me out of the pure operation of the subject and forcing me to occupy simultaneously the position of the object.

Sartre's analysis leads to a conclusion on the ontological level: the other's gaze is the condition for my constitution as an object. Bearing in mind the hiatus between the order of cognition and the order of being, and stripping away the ontological commitment of Sartre's "être-pour-autrui" (being-for-others), we can extract its phenomenological insight: in the agent's experience, the perception of being gazed at genuinely alters the agent's relation to his own action. The agent is no longer merely immersed in the enactment and execution of the action's meaning; he simultaneously realizes that this action is being watched, examined, and judged by others.

This objectification is the core mechanism by which the agent enters the dimension of intersubjectivity. In 1.2.1, we established, through "to be is to be perceivable," the condition for field-forces to enter the action-situation, i.e., the process of the agent

perceiving the other. The gaze is the reverse movement of this perceptual relation: the other's perception of the agent. When these two directions of perception occur simultaneously, the relation between the agent and the other is no longer a unidirectional perceptual relation but constitutes a field of intersubjectivity based on mutual perception. The agent perceives the field-forces, and at the same time perceives that he himself is being perceived by those forces. It is within this mutual perception that the agent and the other jointly enter the dimension of intersubjectivity.

1.2.5.2 The Accumulation of Gazes and the Transparentization of the Field

The gaze of a single bystander is already sufficient to activate the agent's position as object. But when the gaze comes not from a single individual but from a plurality of bystanders, the effect of the gaze undergoes a qualitative transformation.

When there are multiple bystanders in the action-field, and the agent perceives that all of them are gazing at him, the gaze shifts from a possible gaze to a certain gaze. This is a qualitative, structural change brought about by mere quantitative accumulation: the agent can no longer conceive of the possibility of not being gazed at, because the plurality of gazes makes being-seen an irremovable certainty within the action-situation. Even if a particular bystander ceases to gaze, the gazes of the other bystanders continue to sustain the transparency of the field.

I call this the transparentization of the field. In a state of field transparentization, the agent becomes aware that his action no longer belongs solely to himself. It is exposed under a public gaze and becomes something that can be examined, judged, and narrated. The meaning of the action is no longer unilaterally enacted by the agent; it must gain confirmation or correction under the public gaze. The agent can no longer retain complete control over the meaning of his own action in his hands; he must confront the fact that others are also interpreting his action, and that their interpretations will react back upon the action's meaning.

Foucault gave an institutional expression of this in his analysis of "panopticism" (panopticism). In *Surveiller et punir : Naissance de la prison* (Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison), Foucault analyzed Bentham's design of the "Panopticon." As the core concept of Bentham's Panopticon; or, The Inspection-House, the Panopticon stipulates that "Power should be visible and unverifiable." Thus, the Panopticon, as the realization of power, simultaneously contains the two aspects of visibility and unverifiability: "Visible: the inmate will constantly have before his eyes the tall outline of the central tower from which he is spied upon. Unverifiable: the inmate must never know whether he is being looked at at any one moment; but he must be sure that he may always be so."

In the Panopticon, "The more constantly the persons to be inspected are under the eyes of the persons who should inspect them, the more perfectly will the purpose of the establishment be attained." Foucault points out: "Le Panoptique est une machine à dissocier le couple voir-être vu : dans l'anneau périphérique, on est totalement vu, sans jamais voir ; dans la tour centrale, on voit tout, sans être jamais vu. (The Panopticon is a machine for dissociating the see/being-seen dyad: in the peripheral ring, one is totally seen, without ever seeing; in the central tower, one sees everything, without ever being seen.)" "De là l'effet majeur du Panoptique : induire chez le détenu un état conscient et

permanent de visibilité qui assure le fonctionnement automatique du pouvoir. Faire que la surveillance soit permanente dans ses effets, même si elle est discontinuée dans son action ; que la perfection du pouvoir tende à rendre inutile son exercice actuel ; que cet appareil architectural soit une machine à créer et à soutenir un rapport de pouvoir indépendant de celui qui l'exerce ; bref que les détenus soient pris dans une situation de pouvoir dont ils sont eux-mêmes les porteurs. (Hence the major effect of the Panopticon: to induce in the inmate a conscious and permanent state of visibility that assures the automatic functioning of power. To arrange it so that the surveillance is permanent in its effects, even if it is discontinuous in its action; so that the perfection of power tends to render its actual exercise unnecessary; so that this architectural apparatus is a machine for creating and sustaining a power relation independent of the person who exercises it; in short, that the inmates are caught up in a power situation of which they themselves are the bearers.)”

Incorporating the theoretical dimension of “le regard” (the gaze), Foucault’s historical analysis can be elevated to a transcendental structure of the theory of action. “Panopticism” (panopticism) is capable of producing power effects precisely because it exploits the transcendental structure of “le regard”: the gaze objectifies the agent, and the invisibility of the gaze makes this objectification a constant feature of the action-situation. Here, the agent’s action no longer belongs solely to himself; it is exposed within a “panopticism,” and the meaning of the action is not unilaterally enacted by the agent but is confirmed or corrected under the public gaze. The others in the action-field are continuously gazing at and interpreting his action, and their interpretations continuously react back upon the action’s meaning.

1.2.5.3 The Transcendent Position of the Pure Gazer

In 1.2.5.2, we established the mechanism of the transparentization of the field: the plurality of gazes makes being-seen an irremovable certainty within the action-situation. It must be noted that, before differentiation, the gazer, as “Nicht-Ich” (not-I) \cap non-anti-“Ich” (I), possesses a transcendental transcendence with respect to the agent.

In 1.1.2, we established the logical position of the agent as “Ich” (I). Yet the logical position of “Ich” does not exist in isolation; it is always established in its differentiation from “Nicht-Ich” (not-I). Fichte, in his *Grundsätze der gesamten Wissenschaftslehre* (Foundations of the Entire Science of Knowledge), pointed out that at the same moment “Das Ich setzt sich selbst” (The I posits itself), necessarily “Dem Ich wird schlechthin entgegengesetzt ein Nicht-Ich. (A not-I is absolutely opposed to the I.)” In Fichte’s system of the science of knowledge, “Nicht-Ich” is not an empirical other, not an external thing that the “Ich” encounters contingently in experience, but the logical condition that allows the “Ich” to be established. Without “Nicht-Ich” as an opposite, the “Ich” loses its boundary and degenerates into an empty absolute identity. Fichte formulated this structure as the I positing within itself a divisible not-I in opposition to a divisible I, which means that “Ich” and “Nicht-Ich” mutually determine and mutually limit each other within the same field of consciousness. “Das Ich setzt sich selbst, und es ist, vermöge dieses bloßen Setzens durch sich selbst; und umgekehrt: Das Ich ist, und es setzt sein Sein, vermöge seines bloßen Seins. – Es ist zugleich das Handelnde, und das Produkt der Handlung; das Tätige, und das, was durch die Tätigkeit

hervorgebracht wird; Handlung und Tat sind Eins und dasselbe; und daher ist das: Ich bin, Ausdruck einer Tathandlung... (The I posits itself, and by virtue of this mere self-positing it is; and conversely: the I is, and by virtue of its mere being it posits its being. – It is at once the acting and the product of the act; the active and that which is brought forth by the activity; action and deed are one and the same; and hence the ‘I am’ is the expression of a Tathandlung [fact-act]....)”

It is worth noting that, once we strip away his ontological commitments, the form of the relation between Fichte’s “Ich” and “Nicht-Ich”—their common origin and mutual determination—can in fact be seen as an operation of the “semiotic square” within self-identity. The citation of Fichte here, therefore, is more a matter of philosophical-historical genealogy than of strict argumentation.

Hence, there is reason to hold that any logical position of the “Ich” already presupposes a “Nicht-Ich” differentiated from the “Ich.” If “Nicht-Ich” is abolished, the “Ich” has no means of establishing itself. “Ich” and “Nicht-Ich” are not related in a temporal order of succession but are structurally co-constituted. It is precisely in its differentiation from “Nicht-Ich” that the “Ich” acquires its boundary, its determinacy, and its position as subject. It must be stressed that the “Ich” and “Nicht-Ich” at issue here are not “Ding an sich” (things-in-themselves) on the order of being but cognitive-order positions employed to construct subjective identity. Subjective identity is the self-identity of the subject, the cognition that the subject generates of himself. In other words, through the opposition of “Ich” and “Nicht-Ich,” the subject cognizes the selfhood of the “Ich” and also cognizes the world of the “Nicht-Ich.”

Within the action-field, the primordial manifestation of “Nicht-Ich” is precisely the bystander. The bystanders are others that have not yet been differentiated into helpers or opponents; they are merely present, merely gazing, and have not yet been incorporated into the meaning-network defined by the direction of the “Ich’s” action. At the same time, because they have not been incorporated into the meaning-network defined by the direction of the “Ich’s” action, they are also non-anti-“Ich.” Furthermore, because they are “Nicht-Ich” \cap non-anti-“Ich,” the bystanders possess a decisive structural advantage over the agent as “Ich”: transcendence.

This transcendence is manifested on two interrelated levels.

First, the gazer can gaze without being gazed at. In the Sartrean sense, the gaze objectifies the one who is gazed at, thereby granting the gazing subject temporary immunity from the situation of being objectified. “Autrui, dans le phénomène du regard, est par principe ce qui ne peut être objet. Cela ne signifie pas que je ne puisse jamais le regarder comme un objet : je peux regarder celui qui me regarde, mais c’est une autre affaire. Lorsque j’éprouve le regard, autrui m’échappe en tant que sujet. Il est ce par quoi je suis vu, et non ce que je vois. Il est la liberté qui me transcende et que je ne puis transcender. (The Other, in the phenomenon of the gaze, is in principle that which cannot be an object. This does not mean that I can never look at him as an object: I can look at the one who looks at me, but that is another matter. When I experience the gaze, the Other escapes me as subject. He is that by which I am seen, and not what I see. He is the freedom that transcends me and that I cannot transcend.)” The gazer’s look is cast upon the agent, fixing the agent as an object to be examined and judged, while the gazer

himself does not become the direct object of the agent's look. This is not to say that the gazer is physically invisible—in a transparent field, the agent of course knows that others are gazing at him. Rather, it means that the gazer, in the intentional act of gazing, occupies the position of the subject, while the agent, in this intentional act, occupies the position of the object. The gazer, within this specific intentional relation, preserves the transcendence of the subject, while the agent is dragged into the immanence of the object.

Second, the gazer can judge without being judged. The gaze is not only perception but also interpretation. In gazing at the agent, the gazer simultaneously interprets the meaning of the action. Yet the gazer's own act of judging, before he actually intervenes in the action, does not become an object of public scrutiny. The gazer can freely form judgments about the agent while himself being temporarily exempt from the situation of being judged. In other words, the gazer occupies the position of the judge, and the agent occupies the position of the judged.

This transcendent position is the transcendental root of the power effect of the gaze (to be detailed in 1.2.5.4). The gaze is capable of producing power effects not because the gazer empirically possesses more resources, a higher status, or greater strength, but because the gazer occupies the position of "Nicht-Ich" \cap non-anti-"Ich" within the transcendental structure of "Ich" and "Nicht-Ich." Unlike the helper, who is intentionally aligned with the "Ich," or the opponent, who is anti-"Ich," the bystander cannot be assimilated into this simple binary opposition. Before he himself intervenes in the action and becomes a helper or opponent, the bystander always retains a transcendental freedom with respect to the "Ich." He is not defined by the direction of the "Ich's" action, nor captured by the "Ich's" meaning-network. He can freely gaze, freely judge, freely decide whether to intervene—and these very freedoms are what the "Ich" has already partially lost in acting.

Thus, the position of the pure gazer is not an empirical social role but a transcendental logical position. It is the primordial manifestation of "Nicht-Ich" \cap non-anti-"Ich" within the action-field, the structural foothold of transcendence within the dimension of intersubjectivity. Every other who enters the action-field, before adopting any directional intervention, first occupies this very position.

1.2.5.4 The Inhibiting Effect of the Gaze on Differentiation

The most far-reaching impact of the transparentization of the field lies in its reaction back upon the mechanism of differentiation into helpers and opponents. This reaction is not merely a public examination and coordination of differentiations that have already occurred; it begins to operate even before differentiation takes place.

In 1.2.4, we established the differentiation mechanism of the axis of power. The agent differentiates bystanders into helpers or opponents according to the perceived direction of forces, while at this point the bystanders who have not yet taken actual action remain pure gazers.

The gaze of the bystanders is continuously underway. When the bystanders in the action-field begin to gaze at the action, they are not merely potential helpers or opponents; their gaze is simultaneously perceived by other forces in the field—including the agent himself and those neutral others who may become helpers or

opponents. This perception makes the potential helpers and opponents aware, within the gaze, that they themselves may also become objects of the gaze: they discover that, once they openly intervene in the action, whether as helpers or opponents, they themselves will also be exposed under the public gaze and examined as objects.

Logically, the perception of the possibility of the gaze occurs before the act of differentiation. Before deciding whether to intervene, potential helpers and opponents already foresee in advance the risk of objectification that intervention entails. Their intervention would cause them to fall from the transcendent position of the gazer and become the gazed-at object. This fall from subject to object is, in Sartre's sense, the loss of one's own subjectivity; they change from gazers into the gazed-at, from free onlookers into fixed objects. "Je saisis le regard de l'autre au sein même de mon acte comme la solidification et l'aliénation de mes propres possibilités. [...] Autrui comme regard n'est que cela : ma transcendance transcendée. [...] Ainsi, l'être-vu me constitue comme un être sans défense pour une liberté qui n'est pas ma liberté. (I grasp the other's gaze within my very act as the solidification and alienation of my own possibilities. ... The Other-as-gaze is nothing but this: my transcended transcendence. ... Thus being-seen constitutes me as a defenseless being for a freedom that is not my freedom.)"

At this point, in order to preserve their own subjectivity, the potential helpers and opponents are compelled to make a decisive choice: they retreat into the position of the bystander. They choose not to intervene, not to take a stand, not to expose themselves to the scrutiny of the public gaze. By preserving the position of the bystander, they preserve the transcendence of the gazer; they can continue to gaze without being gazed at, to judge without being judged. This retreat is not passive but an active self-preservation. It is a defensive guarding of one's own subjectivity once the subject becomes aware of the risk of objectification.

This constitutes the inhibiting effect of the gaze. The gaze causes potential helpers and opponents to retreat into the position of bystanders, thereby inhibiting the actual generation of helpers and opponents. Forces in the action-field that might have differentiated into allies or enemies remain, because of the gaze, in an undifferentiated neutral state. The agent thereby loses help he might have gained, and is also spared hindrances he might have encountered. At this moment, the action-situation is frozen by the gaze: the forces of others are indeed present, but refuse to intervene.

The inhibiting effect is not limited to helpers and opponents. By the same mechanism, the agent's own action is also inhibited under the gaze. When the agent becomes aware that he is being gazed at by bystanders, he likewise foresees the risk of objectification entailed by further action. Each new step of action will expose him more deeply to the public gaze, making him more thoroughly an object to be examined and judged. To protect his own subjectivity, the agent may also choose to reduce the scope of action, lower the intensity of action, or even suspend action altogether. This is precisely the deepest power effect of "panopticism" (panopticism): it does not operate through coercion, but by making the agent foresee the cost of objectification, thereby causing him to limit his own action of his own accord.

The inhibiting effect is logically posterior to the differentiation of "Ich" and

“Nicht-Ich.” The agent must first distinguish himself from the others in the field in order to perceive the others’ gaze. But it is prior to the actual unfolding of action: before deciding how to act, the agent has already incorporated the inhibiting effect of the gaze into the deliberation of the will. The gaze is not a public judgment carried out after the action is completed, but a disciplinary force that operates before the action even begins.

In this sense, the bystander is not only the matrix of helpers and opponents. Bystanders are also the inhibitors of helpers and opponents; they narrow the passage through which differentiation passes from the potential to the actual. This is the real situation that the agent must face in the public field: he does not act in a clear-cut constellation composed of manifest allies and enemies, but in a field shrouded by the gaze, within which intervention is generally inhibited.

1.2.5.5 Completion of the Axis of Power

The gaze of the bystander completes the final link of the axis of power. At this point, the axis of power exhibits a complete three-layered structure:

First, the bystander as the matrix of differentiation. The other forces in the action-field initially appear as undifferentiated bystanders, who are merely present and have not yet adopted any directional intervention.

Second, the mechanism of differentiation. The agent differentiates bystanders into helpers or opponents according to the perceived direction of forces. This differentiation is an interpretative activity on the part of the agent, while being simultaneously constrained by the actual direction of the forces.

Third, the inhibiting effect of the gaze. The gaze of the bystander transparentizes the action-field. Differentiation is no longer merely a dyadic relation between the agent and the force, but is placed under the public gaze. Every act that produces differentiation faces the structural constraint of the inhibiting effect.

These three layers together constitute the dimension of power that action necessarily faces within its situation. Greimas’s actantial model captured only the result of differentiation in the second layer—the opposition of helper and opponent—while omitting the bystander as matrix and the gaze as a negative feedback mechanism. By supplementing these two layers, the axis of power is transformed from a static scheme of role classification into a dynamic action-structure with an inner normative constraint. Only now is the axis of power—and indeed the entire actantial model—thoroughly completed.

II. A Typology of the Field: The Unfolding of the Action-Field

In 1.1.1, we established that the action-field is the transcendental condition for the possibility of action: action always occurs within a certain field, and the field is the situation implied in the very concept of action. Yet up to now the field has been employed as a unified category. Through the preceding unfolding of the actantial model, we can see that the action-field is not a single, undifferentiated space. It unfolds in at least four distinct dimensions, each possessing its own irreducible mode of operation

and domain of analytic problems.

It must be noted in advance that the distinctions that follow merely describe the dimensions I cognize, and do not purport to be an assertion about the ultimate structure of the action-field. I do not claim that these four dimensions exhaust everything that the action-field is. They are the dimensions that have actually emerged from the transcendental analysis of the concept of action and the deduction of the axis of power; I merely extract them and present them systematically.

2.1 The Physical Field: The Spatio-Temporal Form of Action

The most primordial givenness of action is its occurrence in the physical world. No matter how manifold the meaning of action, no matter how complex the interaction between the agent and others, action always has an irremovable anchor: the body of the agent moves in space and endures in time. Even the most inward decision of the will already presupposes the spatio-temporal form that makes this decision possible, for the decision itself necessarily occurs at a certain moment in time, and the body of the decider, whether it moves or not, necessarily occupies a certain spatial position. Without spatio-temporal form, action could not be localized; it would degenerate into a pure singularity and could not be given as action.

Schopenhauer, in his *Über die vierfache Wurzel des Satzes vom zureichenden Grunde* (On the Fourfold Root of the Principle of Sufficient Reason), anchored the “Satz vom Grunde des Seins” (principle of sufficient reason of being) as spatio-temporal form. “Wir haben schon gesagt, daß zu den wichtigsten Entdeckungen Kants auch diese gehört, daß die Bedingungen der Möglichkeit der Erfahrung, welche in der anschaulichen Welt das allgemeinste Element aller Phänomene ausmachen, Raum und Zeit, auch für sich, abstrakt von ihrem Inhalt, nicht nur abstrakt gedacht, sondern auch unmittelbar angeschaut werden können; und daß diese Anschauung kein von der Erfahrung abgezogenes Phantasma ist, sondern unabhängig von der Erfahrung ist, so sehr, daß vielmehr die Erfahrung als von ihr abhängig gedacht werden muß, da die Eigenschaften des Raums und der Zeit, so wie sie a priori in der Anschauung erkannt werden, für alle mögliche Erfahrung als Gesetze gelten, nach denen diese überall ausfallen muß. (We have already said that among Kant’s most important discoveries is also this, that the conditions of the possibility of experience, which in the intuitive world constitute the most universal element of all phenomena—space and time—can also, by themselves and abstracted from their content, be not only thought abstractly, but also directly intuited; and that this intuition is not a phantasm abstracted from experience, but is independent of experience, so much so that experience must rather be thought of as dependent upon it, since the properties of space and time, as they are known a priori in intuition, hold for all possible experience as laws according to which experience must everywhere turn out.)” Schopenhauer explicitly points out that all existents must be given in time and space. Time and space are not things themselves but the transcendental forms that allow things to appear as phenomena; they deal only with the most basic conditions under which things can exist in the phenomenal realm, i.e., time and space. “Wäre der Raum die alleinige Form dieser Vorstellungsklasse, so gäbe es keine Veränderung: denn Veränderung oder Wechsel ist Sukzession von Zuständen,

Sukzession aber ist nur in der Zeit möglich. Man könnte eben deshalb die Zeit definieren als die Möglichkeit entgegengesetzter Zustände an einem und demselben Dinge. (If space were the sole form of this class of representations, there would be no change: for change or alteration is succession of states, and succession is possible only in time. One could for this very reason define time as the possibility of opposite states in one and the same thing.)” “Wenn allein im Raume, so wäre die Welt starr und unbeweglich, ohne Succession, ohne Veränderung, ohne Thun: ohne Thun ist aber eben auch die Vorstellung der Materie aufgehoben. Wenn allein in der Zeit, so wäre Alles flüchtig, ohne Beharren, ohne Nebeneinander, folglich ohne Zugleich und eben damit ohne Dauer, folglich wieder ohne Materie. Erst aus der Vereinigung von Zeit und Raum erwächst die Materie, d.h. die Möglichkeit des Zugleichseyns und dadurch des Beharens, daraus wieder der Fortdauer des Substanz bei der Veränderung der Zustände. (If merely in space, the world would be rigid and motionless, without succession, without change, without action: but without action the representation of matter itself is abolished. If merely in time, then everything would be fleeting, without permanence, without juxtaposition, consequently without simultaneity and thus without duration, hence again without matter. Only from the union of time and space does matter arise, i.e., the possibility of being-simultaneous and thereby of permanence, and from this again the persistence of substance through the change of states.)” Time is the condition of possibility for all change, and space the condition of possibility for all coexistence. Without spatio-temporal form, no existent could be given to consciousness.

The agent's body, as Schopenhauer's "das unmittelbare Objekt" (immediate object), operates precisely within spatio-temporal form. In 1.1.2, we already established that the minimal object is the body itself; even if no external object is aimed at by the action, the agent's own body already fills the logical position of the object as "das unmittelbare Objekt." The movement of the body necessarily unfolds in space and endures in time. In experiencing himself as capable of initiating an action, the agent necessarily also experiences that this action must occur at a certain time and in a certain space—this is the transcendental condition for action to be given as a phenomenon. "Jeder wahre Act seines Willens ist sofort und unausbleiblich auch eine Bewegung seines Leibes: er kann den Act nicht wirklich wollen, ohne zugleich wahrzunehmen, dass er als Bewegung des Leibes erscheint. Der Willensact und die Action des Leibes sind nicht zwei objectiv erkannte verschiedene Zustände, die das Band der Causalität verknüpft, sie stehn nicht im Verhältniss von Ursache und Wirkung; sondern sie sind Eins und dasselbe, nur auf zwei gänzlich verschiedene Weisen gegeben: einmal ganz unmittelbar und einmal in der Anschauung für den Verstand. (Every true act of his will is at once and inevitably also a movement of his body: he cannot really will the act without simultaneously perceiving that it appears as movement of the body. The act of will and the action of the body are not two objectively cognized different states linked by the bond of causality; they do not stand in the relation of cause and effect; rather, they are one and the same, given only in two completely different ways: once wholly immediately, and once in intuition for the understanding.)” The unity of these two modes of givenness is precisely the primordial manifestation of action in the physical field.

It must be noted that the physical field, as spatio-temporal form, is strictly confined to the level of the cognitive order. “Zeit, Raum und Kausalität sind nicht Bestimmungen des Dinges an sich, sondern gehören nur seiner Erscheinung an, indem sie die Formen unserer Erkenntniß sind. Da alle Vielheit, alles Entstehen und Vergehen nur vermittelt der Zeit, des Raumes und der Kausalität möglich ist; so folgt, daß auch jene nur der Erscheinung zukommen, keineswegs dem Dinge an sich. (Time, space, and causality are not determinations of the thing-in-itself, but belong only to its appearance, since they are the forms of our cognition. Because all multiplicity, all arising and passing away is possible only by means of time, space, and causality, it follows that these too belong only to the appearance, by no means to the thing-in-itself.)” It is not a self-standing entity outside the agent, nor is it some physical container occupying space; it is the spatio-temporal form itself in which action occurs. We can only hold that when action is given to us as a phenomenon, it necessarily bears a spatio-temporal form. The operation experienced by the agent is always already an operation here and now. Spatio-temporal form is the first condition for action to enter cognition, the most primordial condition for the agentive experience to occur.

2.2 The Logical Field: The Cognitive Form of Action

Action occurs in the physical field, acquiring its spatio-temporal localization. But merely operating in time and space is not yet sufficient to make the action a cognized action. A chain of physical events, if not situated within some differential relation, remains merely a meaningless causal chain. For action to be cognized as action, it must be incorporated into logical relations. The transcendental space that makes this logical situating possible is the logical field.

The logical field is not the empirical rules of logic, neither Aristotle’s “συλλογισμός” (syllogism) nor Frege’s “Begriffsschrift” (concept-script). It is the transcendental condition that makes any logical relation—whether identity, difference, opposition, negation, implication—capable of occurring, being identified, and operating. Analogous to how Kant’s “reine Form der sinnlichen Anschauung” (pure form of sensible intuition) makes “empirische Anschauung” (empirical intuition) possible, the logical field makes logical relations possible. Without the logical field, difference could not be established and opposition could not manifest; the agent would be unable to cognize the operations in the physical field as meaningful action. In other words, if the logical field were lost, action would cease to be action and would be merely a chain of physical events.

Schopenhauer, in his *Über die vierfache Wurzel des Satzes vom zureichenden Grunde*, anchored the “Satz vom zureichenden Grunde des Erkennens” (principle of sufficient reason of knowing) as the form of judgment and inference; every judgment must have a ground. “Der Satz vom zureichenden Grunde des Erkennens also, wie ich ihn nenne, und den ich hier in seiner einfachsten Gestalt darlege, ist dieser: Wenn ein Urtheil eine Erkenntniß ausdrücken soll, muß es einen zureichenden Grund haben; wegen dieser Eigenschaft erhält es dann das Prädicat wahr. Die Wahrheit ist also die Beziehung eines Urtheils auf etwas von ihm Verschiedenes, welches dessen Grund (zureichender Grund) genannt wird. (The principle of sufficient reason of knowing,

therefore, as I call it, and which I present here in its simplest form, is this: If a judgment is to express a cognition, it must have a sufficient ground; on account of this property it then receives the predicate true. Truth is thus the relation of a judgment to something different from it, which is called its ground (sufficient ground).” There are grounds to hold that the “principle of sufficient reason of knowing” deals with the logical relations between concepts, making judgment and inference possible.

It must be noted, however, that the logical field is more primordial than the form of judgment. Schopenhauer was concerned with the validity conditions of the derivational relations between propositions, whereas the logical field is concerned with the transcendental space that allows any logical form to appear. It is not the rule of derivation $\therefore P \therefore Q$, but the logical space that allows P and not-P to be distinguished, opposed, and thought. The activity of cognition itself must presuppose a field that allows logical relations to occur. Time is the condition of possibility for all change, space the condition of possibility for all coexistence, and the logical field is the condition of possibility for all logical relations.

Within the logical field, if the agent intends to cognize his own action, he must be able to make at least three fundamental distinctions:

First, he must be able to distinguish “Ich” (I) from “Nicht-Ich” (not-I). In 1.1.2, we established that the differentiation of subject and object is the transcendental condition for action to be cognized. This differentiation itself occurs within the logical field: the agent identifies himself as “Ich” and identifies the others in the field as “Nicht-Ich.” “Ich” and “Nicht-Ich” mutually determine each other within the logical field. If the logical field is abolished, the difference between “Ich” and “Nicht-Ich” cannot be established, and the agent cannot cognize himself as the subject of action.

Second, he must be able to distinguish the meaning of action. In 1.1.4, we established the axis of communication of Sender and Receiver. The sender bestows meaning upon the action; the receiver strips this meaning from the sender’s context, places it into his own context, and generates difference. Meaning is differed and deferred within the logical field; interpretation is always interpretation within the logical field, and difference unfolds its chain within the logical field, while difference itself is also cognized and interpreted within it. Meaning can enter the infinity of difference only within the form of the logical field, and only the formality of the logical field can accommodate the infinity of difference.

Third, he must be able to distinguish the direction of action. Action runs from subject to object and has a definite direction. The intervention of any other force takes this direction as the object of difference and is situated in the logical field as aligned or opposed. In 1.2.2, I noted that the differentiation into helpers and opponents depends on the agent’s judgment of the direction of forces: if the direction of a force is consistent with the direction of action, it is help; if inconsistent, it is hindrance. This very judgment operates within the logical field. The agent compares the direction of the force with the direction of the action, and the act of comparison presupposes that consistency and inconsistency are given within the logical field.

Thus, in every axis of the actantial model, we can discern the operation of the logical field. The axis of desire of subject and object depends on the differentiation of

“Ich” and “Nicht-Ich” within the logical field; the axis of communication of sender and receiver depends on the enactment, reception, and *différance* of meaning within the logical field; the axis of power of helper and opponent depends on the agent’s judgment of the direction of forces, i.e., the operation of relations of consistency and inconsistency within the logical field. Without the logical field, not a single axis of the actantial model could be cognized or spoken of. Every action itself presupposes the operation of logical relations and exists within the logical field.

It must be noted that the logical field is a transcendental structure within the cognitive order, not an entity on the order of being. It is not Plato’s “νοητὸς τόπος” (intelligible realm), nor Hegel’s “der absolute Geist” (absolute spirit), nor some transcendent logical world. It is simply the logical space that the activity of cognition itself must presuppose. The reason why basic logical relations such as identity, difference, opposition, and negation can be thought is that the logical field provides the transcendental condition for their appearance. Given the fundamental hiatus between the order of cognition and the order of being, the thing-in-itself is unknowable; we can cognize only the phenomenon itself. The logical field exists on the level of the cognitive order; it is the logical form that we cannot but presuppose when we cognize action, not a property of the thing-in-itself.

2.3 The Social Field: The Intersubjective Form of Action

Action occurs in the physical field and is cognized in the logical field, but beyond these, action still possesses an irreducible dimension of intersubjectivity. Action is never solitary. Even if the agent acts alone in physical space, even if he has not identified any other, he cannot prove that no other is ever present in the field; he is compelled to admit that he is forced to accommodate the logical position of the other and to place his action, to some degree, within intersubjectivity. The presence of the other is not a physical occupation of space, nor a purely logical relation of difference, but the possibility of the other’s gaze and intervention; in any case, the very existence of the other is already a constitutive part of the action-situation. The transcendental space that makes this intersubjective relation possible is the social field.

The social field is not the empirical institutions of society, group structures, or cultural norms. It is the transcendental condition that makes any intersubjective relation—such as gazing, recognition, identification, judgment—capable of occurring, being perceived, and being responded to. Just as the physical field allows action to occur in time and space, and the logical field allows action to be cognized in differential relations, the social field allows action to be identified in the other’s gaze. Without the social field, the other could not gaze, the agent could not become aware of himself as an object of the gaze, and the meaning of action could not pass from the private sphere into the public sphere. And the public sphere of intersubjectivity upon which the possibility of the gaze rests is already presupposed by the agent; the existence of the social field is thus an incontrovertible fact.

Intersubjectivity, as the field in which multiple wills mutually perceive, mutually recognize, and mutually identify one another, does not belong to Schopenhauer’s domain of problems. Schopenhauer’s is fundamentally a metaphysics of the individual

subject, and thus the problem of intersubjectivity has no corresponding transcendental condition in his framework. The social field addresses precisely this omitted dimension. It concerns not how the individual will is driven, but how action is endowed with public meaning amid the co-presence of multiple wills. This is the unique dimension revealed by Sartre's theory of "le regard" (the gaze), Foucault's "panopticism" (panopticism), and the axis of the bystander in 1.2.3.

In 1.2.5.1, we already disclosed the core mechanism of the social field through Sartre's theory of the gaze. When the agent perceives the presence of others in the field, he perceives not only their existence but also another fact: that the others are gazing at him. This perception has structural consequences: it activates the agent's position as object. The agent is transformed from a mere initiator of action into a composite of subject and object: he is at once the subject in action and the object being gazed at.

This objectification is the primal event in the social field. In the physical field, the agent's body operates in time and space; in the logical field, the agent identifies himself as the I and identifies the others as the not-I. But in the social field, the not-I is no longer an abstract logical position but a concrete other who is gazing at me. The logical difference between the I and the not-I is activated in the social field as a relation of gazing: the other objectifies me, and in the other's gaze I simultaneously become aware that I am not only a subject but also an object.

In 1.2.1, we established, through "to be is to be perceivable," the condition for field-forces to enter the action-situation, i.e., the process of the agent perceiving the other. The gaze is the reverse movement of this perceptual relation: the other's perception of the agent. When these two directions of perception occur simultaneously, the relation between the agent and the other is no longer a unidirectional perceptual relation but constitutes a field of intersubjectivity based on mutual perception. The agent perceives the field-forces, and at the same time perceives that he himself is being perceived by those forces. In this mutual perception, the agent and the other jointly enter the dimension of intersubjectivity.

The social field is precisely the transcendental space that makes this mutual perception possible. It provides the condition for the appearance of the two fundamental relations of gazing and being-gazed-at.

It must be noted that the social field is a transcendental structure within the cognitive order, not an entity on the order of being. It is not Durkheim's "fait social" (social fact), not some collective consciousness transcending the individual, nor Luhmann's "autopoietisches Sozialsystem" (autopoietic social system). It is simply the transcendental condition that allows intersubjective relations to be perceived, identified, and responded to. The reason that the gaze can be experienced as a gaze, that objectification can be experienced as objectification, and that public meaning can be experienced as the confirmation or correction of private meaning—all this is because the social field has already provided the transcendental space in which these relations can appear. The social field is the transcendental condition for action to enter the dimension of intersubjectivity, the transcendental passage through which the agentive experience moves from the private sphere into the public sphere.

2.4 The Cultural Field: The Synthesis of the Three Dimensions

Action occurs in the physical field, is cognized in the logical field, and is identified in the social field. Yet action still has an aspect that cannot be exhausted by the first three dimensions: it is sedimented in time into “a bundle or collection of different perceptions,” forming a “zweite Natur” (second nature) with a specific tendency. No action unfolds with an entirely new cognitive schema; the meaning-resources the agent uses to understand his own action, the cognitive schema with which he appropriates values, and the way he responds to the other’s gaze are never invented out of nothing. They are gradually formed through countless prior actions and will be inherited and transformed in future actions. The transcendental space that makes this historical sedimentation possible is the cultural field.

The cultural field is not a fourth independent dimension alongside the physical, logical, and social fields. It is the synthetic effect of the interaction of the first three dimensions in time.

The physical field provides the spatio-temporal anchor of bodily operation. When a certain mode of bodily operation is repeated and imitated across the bodies of countless agents, it gradually sediments from the contingent operation of individuals into the stable habit of a collectivity. This is the sedimentation of culture in the physical field. The logical field provides the cognitive coordinates of differential relations. When a certain mode of cognizing and appropriating value is repeated, confirmed, and transmitted across the cognitions of countless agents, it gradually sediments from the contingent judgment of individuals into the stable norms of a collectivity. Value-conceptions, classificatory systems, cognitive habits, and so on, are all sedimentation of culture in the logical field. The social field provides the space of intersubjectivity. It is the necessary passage through which the contingent reaction of the individual enters the collective gaze and becomes a collective consensus.

The cultural field is not the mere sum of these three dimensions. It is their historical synthesis; it is the product of the continuous operation, mutual interweaving, and joint sedimentation of the physical, logical, and social dimensions in time. Any cultural tradition necessarily contains simultaneously the bodily techniques from the physical field, the value distinctions from the logical field, and the gazes and judgments from the social field. These three dimensions operate simultaneously in every cultural practice; in countless repetitions they mutually reinforce one another, sediment jointly, and eventually form a relatively stable meaning-network that can be transmitted across generations.

Cognitive schemas are mutable; they vary with history, culture, and individual experience. The cultural field is precisely the transcendental space in which cognitive schemas can be generated, sedimented, and transmitted. The cognitive schema of a specific culture is neither an arbitrary personal construction nor the creation of some collective consciousness; it is gradually sedimented within the cultural field through the continuous operation of countless agents across the physical, logical, and social dimensions.

The cultural field allows cognitive schemas to be relatively stable. Once a cognitive schema has sedimented within the cultural field, it possesses a pre-givenness

for later agents. The agent does not need to develop a cognitive schema from scratch but acts in a world where numerous cognitive schemas already exist. Language, customs, institutions, traditions—these are all cognitive schemas sedimented in the cultural field; they constitute the background of meaning that later agents must confront. At the same time, it also allows cognitive schemas to change. Every action is a reactivation of the sedimented cognitive schema and, simultaneously, a re-carving of it. In employing tradition, the agent also transforms it in *différance*. When countless agents adjust bodily techniques in the physical field, modify value distinctions in the logical field, and change the manner of responding to the gaze in the social field, these tiny *différences* accumulate within the cultural field, eventually leading to the historical transformation of the cognitive schema. In sum, the cultural field is both the field of existence of cognitive schemas and the field of their change.

Glossary

Action-field

The transcendental situation-pole presupposed by every action; the dimension in which action necessarily unfolds.

The Acted

The unknowable, noumenal ground that triggers the phenomenological experience of the **agentive**.

Adjuvant/Opposant (Helper/Opponent)

In the actantial model, the two logical modalities of influence field-forces exert on action—helping (coinciding with the action's direction) or hindering (opposing it).

The Agentive

The phenomenological experience of voluntary autonomy undergone by the agent in acting; the manifestation of the acted within the cognitive order.

Axis of communication

The Destinateur/Destinataire (Sender/Receiver) axis, governing the enactment and reception of the action's meaning.

Axis of desire

The Sujet/Objet (Subject/Object) axis, governing the subject's seeking of the object.

Axis of power

The Adjuvant/Opposant (Helper/Opponent) axis, complemented by the bystander, governing the influence of field-forces on action.

Bystander (the neutral)

The undifferentiated logical position from which helpers and opponents emerge; the common matrix of differentiation and bearer of the gaze.

Cognitive order (law of cognition)

The domain of phenomena and transcendental conditions of experience, distinct from the order of being.

Différance

The simultaneous differing and deferring of meaning along the axis of communication; the infinite movement that prevents meaning from being fixed.

Field transparentization

The state in which the plurality of gazes renders being-seen an irremovable certainty, exposing the agent's action to constant public scrutiny.

Hiatus between order of being and order of cognition

The fundamental gap acknowledging that the noumenal (the acted, the thing-in-itself) is unknowable; we know only its phenomenal manifestation.

Inhibiting effect of the gaze

The mechanism by which potential helpers and opponents retreat into the bystander position to avoid objectification, thereby freezing the action-field.

Intersubjectivity

The dimension of mutual perception, recognition, and identification among multiple wills, activated by the gaze.

Meta-action (atomic action / simple action)

The subject's direct operation of the will upon the immediate object (the body); the indivisible phenomenological atom of action.

Modèle actantiel

Greimas's narratological model reducing narrative agents to six roles in three pairs: Subject/Object, Sender/Receiver, Helper/Opponent.

Objectification

The process by which the gaze fixes the agent as an object to be examined and judged, stripping him of pure subjectivity.

Order of being (law of being)

The noumenal realm of the thing-in-itself, which lies beyond the boundary of cognition.

Panopticism (panopticisme)

Foucault's analysis of the Panopticon, generalized here as a transcendental structure of power operating through visibility and the gaze.

Pure gazer

A bystander occupying the logical position of "Nicht-Ich \cap non-anti-Ich," who gazes and judges from a transcendent position without being directly gazed at or judged.

Regard (le regard / the gaze)

The other's look that objectifies the agent and activates the intersubjective dimension; a central power mechanism.

Will-chain

The unified intentionality threading through multiple meta-actions in a complex action, projecting itself as a series of agentive experiences.

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